

The Future for Robust Design Research

The First International Symposium on Robust Design

Thomas J. Howard

Head of Robust Design Group

DTU Mechanical Engineering
Department of Mechanical Engineering

How much force to press on a lid?

Robust Design: The Transfer Function

Robust Design: The Transfer Function

Robust Design: Quality loss function

WP2 (PhD 2)

The relationship between variation in multiple DPs and multiple functional performance (FP) parameters

Robust Design: Quality loss function

WP2 (PhD 2)

The relationship between variation in multiple DPs and multiple functional performance (FP) parameters

from Forslund, Karin, M. Karlsson, and Rikard Söderberg (2013)

Robust Design: Quality loss function

WP1 (PhD 1)

The relationship between variation in the FRs and the perceived quality of the product (Q)

WP2 (PhD 2)

The relationship between variation in multiple DPs and multiple functional performance (FP) parameters

Robust Design: Process Capabilities

WP1 (PhD 1)

The relationship between variation in the FRs and the perceived quality of the product (Q)

WP2 (PhD 2)

The relationship between variation in multiple DPs and multiple functional performance (FP) parameters

WP3 (PhD 3)

Robust Production and Process Capabilities Data Bases and Design Guide

Join our team?

Vacancies in Robust Design Research

1. Senior Researcher in Robust Design

(Equivalent to Associate Professor without teaching)

Responsible for driving the research content of the robust design programme with Novo Nordisk and PhD project supervision.

2. PhD Researcher in Robust Design and Process Capability assessment

Good knowledge of Mechanical and Production engineering required.

Contact Tom Howard – thow@mek.dtu.dk

Horizon 2020 Bid: A global Process Capability Database

Thomas J. Howard & Tobias Eifler
DTU Robust Design Group

The traditional approach to tolerance design

1. Designer decides on concept
2. Sets geometry to meet specification
3. Sets the tolerance limits to hold within specification
4. Passes to production
5. Production may decide/find-out that the design is out of process capability
6. Designer re-designs.

Design to Process Capability (DtPC)

1. Designer decides on concept
2. Sets geometry to meet specification
3. Checks that the features are within process capabilities of the production
4. Redesigns if required
5. Sends to the production for approval.

How do we do this?

- We need good data, and
- An easy way to use the data in design

Current approaches include

Tolerance standards and guidebooks

- Conflicting data between standards
- Old data
- Only on Linear dimensions and Holes/Shafts

Asking Process Capability Expert for opinion

- Subjective
- Relies on expert's availability
- Relies on whether expert can recall a similar case

How to **GET** the data:

Populating a process capability database base

How to **USE** the data:

Populating a process capability database base

Bringing Big Data into Manufacturing

The motivation

- To create a new and superior Danish/European Tolerance Standard, based on big data.
- To allow of Process Capability Benchmarking
- To enable a Process Capability Certification Programme to certify sub-suppliers in the supply chain.
- To develop an interface that Designer can Design to Process Capability (DtPC)
- To have living/updating process capability data

Principle agreement

Expression of Interest

Hopeful 😊

Looking for interested partners to join the proposal.

Closing of I SoRD14

The **First** International Symposium on Robust Design

Your use of software

Robust Design Methods, Activities and Software

- Large spread in used methods
 - Most used are Tolerance design, DOE and kinematic design
- Low knowledge and usage on VMEA and Functional failure design
- Excel is by far the most used software tool for most activities
- VMEA and axiomatic design is not well supported by software

The proceedings – Open Access 😊

The screenshot shows the ISO RD 2014 CPH website. At the top, there are logos for DTU, novo nordisk, and Valcon. A navigation bar includes links for Home, Downloads, Programme, Accommodation, Travel, Submission, Delegates, Contact, and Registration. The main content area is divided into three sections:

- Proceedings**: Features a book cover icon, a download icon, and a button labeled "Download full book". The DOI is listed as 10.11581/DTU.00000006.
- Single papers**: Features a document icon, a button to "View a full list of the papers the programme", and a button to "Download the papers from Proceedings.dtu.dk".
- Robust Design Workshop - A forensic Engineering Case**: Includes a welcome message and a list of external links:
 - Please use the free [eDrawings Viewer](#) (choose [eDrawings viewer only](#)) in order to view the CAD files
 - Information on material properties are available in material databases (e.g. [matweb.com](#))
 - See [here](#) for Information on achievable tolerance windows in production processes

At the bottom of the workshop section, there are four colored buttons: Introduction (blue), CAD Files (red), Workbook (green), and Presentation Template (yellow).

Thanks to our reviewers:

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Thankyou to the ISoRD14 Organising Committee:

Thomas J. Howard (Chair)

Tobias Eifler (Co-Chair)

Søren Pedersen

Martin Ebro

Moritz Göhler

Andreas Rafn

Aryan Christiansen

Jonas Olesen

We'd like to thank two people in particular

Andreas Rafn

&

Aryan Christiansen

DTU ROBUST DESIGN DAY 2015

The Robust Design Day will be an **Annual, Single Day event** for on Danish Industry and Academia.

The event will feature invited speakers and interactive discussions and activities as with ISoRD.

Please expect an invitation, we look forward to your participation!

I SoRD16 ?????

The 2nd International Symposium on Robust Design

2014

2016

Prof. Wartzack and the Chair of Engineering Design proudly welcomes you to the ISoRD 2016 in Erlangen!

- ...in the “center” of Europe (Nürnberg region)
- ...in one of the economically strongest regions of Germany

Selected Topics of the ISoRD 2016:

- Robust Design Methodology
- Tolerance Management / Analysis
- Design for Six Sigma
- Process Capability Evaluation
- ...

Further Information:

- robustdesign.org/ISoRD

ISoRD 2016 in Erlangen Impressions

Bearings and Mountings

Bearings and Mountings

Tribological Coating Systems

Dimensional Management

**From the creative idea
to the systematically optimized product**

Virtual Product Development

Teaching and Education

Lightweight Design

Tribological Coating Systems

Systems in Motion

Tolerance Analysis and Tolerance Synthesis for Systems in Motion

Discrete Geometry TA

Tolerance Analysis based on discrete Geometry Representations

ISoRD 2016 in Erlangen Partners...

... in the science world

... international

... and with industry sector

